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FACULTY RESEARCH FINAL IMRAD (Publishable) MANUSCRIPT

STUDENT LEADERSHIP ENGAGEMENT IN HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS: A LOCAL GOVERNMENT UNIT AND UNIVERSITY INITIATIVE

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ABSTRACT

Developing leadership in students is a challenging task and it is an established mandate of higher educational institutions. This study endeavored to provide relevant information on students' portrait of leadership, motivations in seeking out leadership opportunities and critical thinking disposition in six domains, such as: open-mindedness; inquisitiveness; systematicity; truth-seeking; analyticity; and self-confidence. It utilized a combination of qualitative and quantitative approaches through descriptive – comparative research method. Findings showed that student leaders perceived that leaders are not only making orders but making themselves an example and inspire the members of the organization. Leaders are not ideal but practical. Leaders should perform what they preach and they should not focus on theories but more on action. Leadership should be selfless and focus on service to the humanity. Students serve neither at the expense of others nor at a particular prize or something in return. They serve the studentry unselfishly and do not expect material or non-material benefits. The motivations of students to seek out leadership opportunities could be personal motivation, motivation from other people or circumstances and at higher level meaning of life and work. On the level of critical thinking disposition of student leaders in all areas of being open-minded, inquisitive, analytic, truth seeking, systematic and self-confident generally manifests modest desirability. Likewise, findings showed that school, gender, year level, position held, course and trainings attended are not considered factors that could affect the student leaders' perception on leadership. A student leadership program is proposed as an off-shoot of the study.

Keywords: *Civic life, critical thinking, motivations and portrait of leadership, responsible citizenship*

INTRODUCTION

"We cannot always build the future for our youth, but we can build our youth for the future" (Franklin D. Roosevelt). Student leadership is one of the identified priorities of higher education institutions (HEIs). The development of leadership capabilities has been championed by many universities and colleges around the world. This was integrated under the United Nations' sustainable development goal (SDG) 4 on inclusive and equitable quality education and promotion of lifelong learning and SDG 11 which focuses on promoting peaceful and inclusive societies at all levels, providing access to justice for all, and building effective and accountable institutions. Skalicky *et al.* (2018) and Osmani *et al.* (2015) also claimed that the development of competitive edge and promotion

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of lifelong learning of students prompted universities to pay closer attention to the development of graduate attributes including leadership qualities. This priority area in HEIs is pervasive which ranges from the highest level of institutional plan down to specific units, programs and projects.

In the Philippines, Section 4 of CHED Memorandum Order No. 09, series of 2013 provides that educational institutions have the responsibility to form individuals who can later become productive citizens of the country and the world. This responsibility is not only confined to the teaching and development of job skills, but also to the acquisition of life skills and values. Ultimately, the individuals produced by the educational institution should be able to contribute positively to the progress of the country, and to the improvement of human conditions. HEIs therefore must systematically and deliberately address this end objective of producing citizens suited to the aims of the country and of humanity.

Aside from the aforesated mandate, this topic on student leadership is part of Saint Mary's University priority research areas, particularly on lifelong learning and transformative studies. It would also be a response to the programs and projects of the provincial local government unit (PLGU) of Nueva Vizcaya particularly on the newly promulgated ordinance on the creation of Provincial Youth Development Council (PYDC) and other programs of the government being undertaken for dynamic and responsible leadership of future leaders.

All these discourses and established structures on student leadership also form a considerable part of the C3 framework in the Social Studies/Sciences education, namely: College, Career and Civic Life. Through the various courses, there is a great emphasis on the acquisition and application of knowledge, skills and values to prepare students for their duties and responsibilities as fully participating citizens not only in the Philippines but in the whole world as well. Hence, studies to enrich, strengthen and make the courses in the Social Studies/Sciences pragmatic and relevant are imperative in the attainment of the abovementioned goals and objectives. This study focused on the portrait of student leadership engagement, students' motivation to seek out leadership and critical thinking disposition. The proposed program based on the salient findings of the study shall be submitted to the PYDC for a meaningful and relevant collaboration between SMU and the PLGU of Nueva Vizcaya.

METHODOLOGY

This study made use of a combination of qualitative and quantitative approaches in research. The method for qualitative design was descriptive which deals with the portrait of student leadership and motivations in seeking out leadership opportunities. Meanwhile, the method for the quantitative design was descriptive-comparative and this deals with the profile variables, critical thinking dispositions and comparison of responses when grouped according to profile variables. The technique in gathering data was through a survey administered in a face-to-face modality.

The study was conducted in six known HEIs in Nueva Vizcaya, Philippines, namely: Saint Mary's University, Nueva Vizcaya State University Bayombong and Bambang Campuses, Kings College of the Philippines - Bambang, PLT College, Inc., and Aldersgate College. Respondents came from these HEIs since all of which comply with CHED mandate and other national and international declarations in providing an avenue and opportunities for students to develop their leadership capabilities.

The respondents were three student leaders in the selected organization both co-curricular and extra-curricular, particularly the President and two other officers. Table 1 shows the distribution of the respondents.

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Table 1.

Prospective Respondents of the Study

Name of School	Respondents
1. Saint Mary's University	
a. Supreme Student Council	3
b. Co-curricular Organization (15)	45
c. Extra-curricular Organization (10)	30
2. Nueva Vizcaya State University (Bambang Campus)	
a. Supreme Student Council	3
b. Co-curricular Organization (15)	45
c. Extra-curricular Organization (10)	30
3. Nueva Vizcaya State University (Bayombong Campus)	
a. Supreme Student Council	3
b. Co-curricular Organization (15)	45
c. Extra-curricular Organization (10)	30
4. PLT College Inc.	
a. Supreme Student Council	3
b. Co-curricular Organization (10)	30
c. Extra-curricular Organization (8)	24
5. Kings College of the Philippines	
a. Supreme Student Council	3
b. Co-curricular Organization (10)	30
c. Extra-curricular Organization (8)	24
6. Aldersgate College	
a. Supreme Student Council	3
b. Co-curricular Organization (10)	30
c. Extra-curricular Organization (8)	24
Total	405

Data were gathered through the: *Portrait of Student Leadership and Motivations in seeking out Leadership Opportunities* adopted from the study of Aminitehrani (2017) *California Critical Thinking Disposition Inventory (CCTDI) Turkish Version* by Gökhan (2013). This measures the 'willing' dimension in the expression "willing and able" to think critically." This is intended to measure the critical thinking aspects of student-leaders. It has six sub-dimensions namely: (1) open-mindedness with 12 items; (2) inquisitiveness with eight items; (3) systematicity with six items; (4) truth-seeking with seven items; (5) analyticity with 11 items; and (6) self-confidence with seven items.

The researchers first finalized the proposal based on the suggestions of the panel of examiners. After which, a letter was crafted which was sent to the dean of the Students' Affairs and Services of all the aforesated six HEIs for the collection of pertinent data and approval to conduct the study. When the approval had been secured, the researchers proceeded to floating of the survey questionnaires to the respondents. The researchers employed research enumerators who did not have direct or personal relationship with the identified officers of the selected organization. These enumerators were the ones who administered the instrument at a particular time and space agreed upon with the respondents. The researchers did not ask the dean of student affairs or subject teachers to administer the research instrument. After that, collection of the questionnaires from respondents followed. The retrieved questionnaires were then tallied, recorded and analyzed using various tools or systems like MS Word, Excel, and the SPSS. The writing followed after the processing of data gathered.

The profile variables (gender, year level, position held, course; and leadership training attended) were presented using frequency and percent. The identification and analysis of student leaders' portrait of leadership and their motivations in seeking out leadership opportunities were coded and thematically clustered. The student leaders were assigned pseudonyms and the deductive way of writing was used. The levels of critical thinking dispositions of student-leaders were presented

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through mean ratings and standard deviations. Table 2 shows the mean scale scoring, qualitative descriptions and interpretations:

Table 2.
Mean Score Scale, Qualitative Descriptions and Interpretations

Mean Scale	Qualitative Descriptions	Interpretations
1.00-1.49	Strongly Disagree	Conditions surrounding the item manifest intense undesirability in critical thinking disposition of student leaders
1.50-2.49	Disagree	Conditions surrounding the item manifest modest undesirability in critical thinking disposition of student leaders
2.50-3.49	Agree	Conditions surrounding the item manifest modest desirability in critical thinking disposition of student leaders
3.50-4.00	Strongly Agree	Conditions surrounding the item manifest intense desirability in critical thinking disposition of student leaders

The comparison of the level of the student-leaders' critical thinking aspects when grouped according to profile variables were analyzed through parametric tests. T-test for gender and ANOVA for year level, course, position held, and leadership training attended.

RESULTS

Student Leaders on Leadership Engagement

In this study, student leaders were asked on their own definition and conceptualization of leadership. The responses were clustered into four themes, namely: definition of leadership; importance of leadership to society; qualities or traits of a good leader; and reasons on how people become leaders.

For the definition of leadership, first was the idea that leaders are not only making orders but making themselves an example, the model of the group and the leader that inspire the members of the organization. Wency, one of the SCC officers, shared that, *we all know that leadership is simply causing other people do what leaders want but for me a true leader takes people where they go, inspire others to dream more learn more and become more.* In this definition, Paula, also an SCC officer, added that *leadership pertains to an actions that is empowering every strata of humanity despite of differences and also being core of goodness and positivity.* Another definition was related to the principle that leaders are not ideal but practical. Leaders should perform what they preach, and they should not focus on theories but more on action. This definition could be reflected on the following responses: Rey, LC officer – *For me, Leadership is when one knows how to lead with words and actions;* Mia, LC officer – *Leadership is not a position, it's an action;* and Gray, LC officer - *Leadership pertains to an actions that is empowering every strata of humanity despite of differences and also being core of goodness and positivity.* Finally, on the definition of leadership, they shared that student leaders should have selfless service to humanity. Students serve neither at the expense of others nor at a particular prize or something in return. They serve the studentry unselfishly and do not expect material or non-material benefits.

For the respondents' view regarding the importance of leadership to society, leadership is perceived as important in many ways, but their common idea was that, with good leadership, the society could be productive, guided and directed to a certain direction. If there is no leadership, the society will be in chaos and not in order. Examples of their responses were: Rene, SCC officer – *Leadership is important because it help us to manage or deal with problems when things get worse* and Dolly, LC officer - *With leadership, our society would be productive and organized. Leaders are the ones who will push their people to be the best version of themselves and inspire them to pursue their dreams.*

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The third theme under this part on definition and conceptualization of a leader relates with the qualities of traits of a good leader. The student leaders surveyed have a good collection of desirable and long standing qualities or traits of a good leader. Some of these are considered knowledge based, others are skills and values needed by leaders to lead their constituents. Among these, the most mentioned trait is *honesty*, followed by *good in communicating* and *being responsible*. Other qualities commonly seen in their responses are being : *confident, empathic, helpful, committed, has maximum of tolerance, listens to others, accepts his/her faults, helpful, has energy and enthusiasm, innovative/creative, good decision maker, influencer, with morals, ethics and fidelity, and open-minded.*

The last theme under this part on definition and conceptualization of a leader relates with the reasons of becoming leaders and whether leaders are naturally born or not. Some of the responses were: Sheena, SCC officer – *If they did something good and that goodness will benefit us and good influence to our fellowmen* and Johnny, LC officer – *There's no specific ways or steps to become a leader. Becoming a leader can be acquired through succession, election, appointment and even through evil means. Then it depends to a leader that came through any of the above-mentioned means on what kind of leader she/he becomes.*

Motivations of students to seek out leadership opportunities

The motivations of students to seek out leadership opportunities could be clustered into two themes, and these are their personal motivation and motivation from other people or circumstances. Their personal motivation comes with what they believe in life, their capabilities, principles, choices, own passion, advocacy and the like. In this light, some of the responses provided by the respondents were: Gina, LC officer – *Because of their sense of responsibility and good advocacy and principles in life;* Greg, LC officer – *These people become leaders because they have the passion to lead, serve and inspire;* Prima – SCC Officer – *People become leaders because others believe that they can make a change/difference;* Ralph, LC officer – *If it's literally, they are elected;* Frany, SCC officer – *Most of the time people become leaders Because they are chosen, some become leaders because they were popular, Some are made just to lead but the best leaders are those who serve without people's choice or vote;* and Tony, LC officer – *Perhaps because of the situation. Sometimes the situation dictates or requires a leader.*

Level of Critical Thinking Disposition

For open-mindedness, the respondents disagreed on the following: *Being open-minded means you don't know what's true and what's not*, this was also the aspect with the lowest rating; *Reading is something I avoid, if possible;* *Being open-minded about different world views is less important than people think;* *Things are as they appear to be;* and *Others are entitled to their opinions, but I don't need to hear them.* On the other hand, they agreed that: *If there were four reasons in favor and one against. I'd go with the four;* *Tests that require thinking, not just memorization, are better for me*, this was also the statement with the highest rating; *Foreigners should study our culture instead of us always trying to understand theirs;* *I look for facts that support my views, not facts that disagree.* For inquisitiveness, the results showed that the student leaders agreed on the following: *Others admire my intellectual curiosity and inquisitiveness;* *Complex problems are fun to try to figure out;* and *No matter what the topic, I am eager to know more about it.* Meanwhile, student leaders strongly agreed with: *Studying new things all my life would be wonderful;* *I look forward to learning challenging things*, this was their highest rating; and *I really enjoy trying to figure out how things work.*

In terms of systematicity, it was found out that the student leaders disagreed on the following: *It's easy for me to organize my thoughts;* *People say I rush into decisions too quickly;* *When I have to deal with something really complex, it's panic time;* and *People think I procrastinate about making decisions.*

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On the other hand, they agreed on these statements: *I'm proud that I can think with great precision, and I pretend to be logical, but I'm not.* With regard to truth-seeking attribute, the student leaders agreed that: *Everyone always argues from their own self-interest, including me and I believe what I want to believe,* this is also their highest rating. Meanwhile, they disagreed on the following: *Most subjects are uninteresting and not worth taking; Some subjects in high school waste so much time; Being impartial is impossible when I'm discussing my own opinions; It's just not that important to keep trying to solve difficult problems; and I know what I think, so why should I pretend to ponder my choices.*

For the aspect of analyticity, the surveyed student leaders agreed to most of the items except for three that they strongly agreed. They strongly agreed on the following: *I must have grounds for all my beliefs; People need reasons if they are going to disagree with another's opinion,* this was also their highest rating; and *Getting a clear idea about the problem at hand is the first priority.* On the other hand, they agreed on the following: *It bothers me when people rely on weak arguments to defend good ideas; I always focus the question before I attempt to answer it; I pride myself on coming up with creative alternatives; You could describe me as logical; and Learn everything you can, you never know when it could come in handy.* For self-confidence, the students agreed on these statements: *Others look to me to establish reasonable standards to apply to decisions and Others look to me to decide when the problem is solved* followed by the following: *My peers call on me to make judgments because I decide things fairly; I take pride in my ability to understand the opinions of others; Others look to me to keep working on a problem when the going gets tough; I'm known for approaching complex problems in an orderly way; and I'm good at developing orderly plans to address complex problems.*

Comparisons on the level of critical thinking dispositions of student-leaders when grouped according to profile variable

For the comparisons, those with significant differences were on open-mindedness for school and sex variables; analyticity for school variable; open-mindedness and truth-seeking for trainings attended variable. For the school variable, only in the analyticity aspect yielded to a significant difference and in the multiple comparisons only the responses between School A and B had a significant difference in response. In general, however, all the analyzed data revealed that in most aspects of leadership, there is no significant difference of the responses when grouped according to school, gender, year level, course and trainings attended, variables.

DISCUSSIONS

Student Leaders on Leadership Engagement

Leadership varies in different conditions and contexts. Its variations greatly depend on the kinds of people, places and time. One of the important groups in the educational institutions where leadership play a vital role is the studentry. Student leaders in different co-curricular and extra-curricular organizations perform numerous roles from being errands to faculty and school officials to functioning as liaisons between students and school's staff, teachers and administrators. HEIs prepare students from these simple roles to becoming leaders of their own duly recognized organizations. Fredricks et al. (2011), as cited by Angelle (2018) claimed that universities need to prepare students in the ever-changing world by equipping them with 21st century skills such as proficiency in problem solving, critical thinking, communication, and collaboration.

To enhance student leadership engagement, knowledge, skills and values needed must be addressed efficiently through co-curricular and extra-curricular organizations where students are actively engaged and involved in relevant educational and civic activities (Angelle, 2018). Ferlazzo

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(2017) stated that “engagement is not about baiting a hook. It’s about helping students find their spark and make their own fire”. More than ever, HEIs are challenged to persist in inculcating and molding the highest virtues to students despite obstacles, difficulties and the lure of power, greed, fame and material things. Students are engaged in various forms of leadership as they take active role in their own organizations. Some actually engaged in undertakings that are specifically intended to develop leadership capabilities alongside, within and outside such as student government, leadership award programs, socio-civic societies and international assemblies. Others participate through student-facing activities like peer tutoring, student study group, campus tour and volunteering in community extension and outreach activities.

Motivations of students to seek out leadership opportunities

How can students become leaders in school? This is one of the questions needed to be answered for leaders are not born but are made. More specifically, leaders are products of time and space. Pritchard (2022) opined that to be a leader needs dynamic and high level of engagement in school activities. One must take on a leadership position from leading a group in class, a committee, and the whole university. Another is to be a good role model which entails not necessarily a leader but also a good follower. There could be a lot more, but scholars also posited that leadership development must commence the earliest possible and this must be given attention by administrators and decision makers in various fields both the private and public sector (Adams *et al.*, 2018; Keselman *et al.*, 2015).

The millennium age of educational leadership opens a new perspective towards student leadership (Black *et al.*, 2014). The idea of student leadership in the 21st century has risen (Adams & Velarde, 2018), the call for student leadership gaining in momentum, as various enhanced leadership models and trends are developed for students (Tan & Adams 2018; Tie, 2012). As leaders of tomorrow, it is imperative that student leaders grasp an understanding of the many leadership styles, know the leadership models and exposed to leadership development programs that enables them to increase their knowledge, competence, skills and capabilities as leaders. Student leadership development is now the responsibility of all members of the learning community (Dugan & Komives, 2010) and schools have a responsibility to prepare students to lead (Adams *et al.*, 2018).

With the term “leadership” itself being a difficult one for experts to agree upon, it is expected that defining leadership for adolescents or student leaders is not also an easy task. How does one define youth leadership? White (2014) conducted a literature review aiming to define this term and showed that there is an understanding of adolescent leadership as training activity or process driven. The answer may be to turn to the youth themselves in assistance for defining this term. By doing this, an increase in youth engagement in leadership may be seen among today’s adolescents (Mortensen, *et al.*, 2014). This is where the importance of this study on student leadership comes in. It is the understanding of the lived experiences of student leaders about some aspects of leadership such as their conceptualizations of leadership and their motivation in seeking out leadership opportunities.

Critical Thinking Disposition

Critical thinking dispositions can be interpreted as a tendency for a person to think critically. Only someone who has the critical thinking disposition will use his critical thinking skills. Thus, it can be said that the critical thinking disposition is a very important thing owned by students. By having a high critical thinking disposition, students will be able to use their critical thinking skills that can assist them in mastering the subject matter learned and solving problems encountered in everyday life. For openmindedness, the findings reflect that the student leaders appeared to be following one good quality of leadership and this is open-mindedness. The leaders know based on their responses which

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are desirable and what is not. These findings could be related to the ideas of Lynch (2018) who stated that the education world changes quickly and so leaders must also be open to these changes. Student leaders as they mature learn how to deal with variety of ideas, if they could not develop the sense of being open-minded then they may not be able to deliver what the studentry desires.

With regard inquisitiveness, the student leaders were aware that this plays a big role in leadership. Their ability to know more and eagerness to explore new things could really help them a lot, especially that there will really be more things and more challenges to occur in their stint as leaders. Their strong agreements like the idea that studying things is wonderful, the attitude of always looking forward to learning challenging things and enjoying figuring out how things work show the optimistic side of being a leader. Without these, students will become limited, static and with inadequate knowledge and skill to govern the student body. In terms of systematicity, the results reflect that the student leaders knew that being systematic entails thinking with great precision, becoming logical, organization of thoughts carefully before acting, not rushing any decision or judgment. For student leaders to function systematically, they should work with data, hard facts and group of advisors. Student leaders could not work by themselves and should not decide on their own, especially if what at stakes is the future of the students whom they govern. They should not make decisions abruptly just to conclude their leadership or just to show that they did something. Their leadership will not actually be judged during the time that they were leaders but after the effects of their action are being felt or experienced by the study body.

For truth-seeking the findings imply that the student leaders perceived this as one important aspect of being a leader. All of the items were written in the negative form and so these are undesirable attitudes for a leader who is a truth-seeker. Thus, their disagreements show that they know the characters that build up a leader who wants to pursue the truth and avoid those unwanted ones. If one leader says something, this could be construed to be whether truth or deception, of course, we do not want to choose the second but we seek for the truth. Leaders then when they say something must speak for the truth or should always be interpreted as the right one. The results on analyticity could mean that the student surveyed are analytic leaders. Based on their responses, they perceived things as not only what they should be but they really want to clear things and have to rely on solid grounds before they say and do something. In particular, the highest that they strongly agreed with is the idea that reasons should guide their actions, that before they disagree with another's opinion, they must based this on valid reasons. With the high rating on the statement that leaders should have grounds in all their beliefs and getting a clear idea about a problem at hand is the first priority manifest that the student leaders are clear with their thoughts and really dedicated on their positions as student leaders.

The results on self-confidence could mean that the student leaders had great self-confidence and they value the things that could make them one. Having strong self-confidence must really be one of the traits that student leaders should possess but like being analytic, this should not be abused. When leaders become too much confident with themselves, they tend to undermine other aspects that may also undermine the rights and privileges of other students. When leaders are self-confident, their meta-skills, psychological prowess, motivation and persistence could really be magnified. The best of this is that self-confidence plays an important role in a leader's ability to influence his collaborators' behaviors, thoughts and emotions, in large part, by strengthening his integrity, since integrity is a cornerstone not only of leadership but also of trust.

CONCLUSIONS

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From all the responses, student leaders perceived that leaders are not only making orders but making themselves an example, the model of the group and the leader that inspire the members of the organization. Leaders are not ideal but practical. Leaders should perform what they preach and they should not focus on theories but more on action. Leadership should be selfless and focus on service to the humanity. Students serve neither at the expense of others nor at a particular prize or something in return. They serve the studentry unselfishly and do not expect material or non-material benefits. Finally, responses reflect desirable traits that places leaders with knowledge, skills and desirable values who leads the organization in achieving their vision and missions. The motivations of students to seek out leadership opportunities could be personal motivation, motivation from other people or circumstances and at higher level meaning of life and work. On the level of critical thinking disposition of student leaders in all areas of being open-minded, inquisitive, analytic, truth seeking, systematic and self-confident generally manifests modest desirability. The responses on gender variable has a bearing only in the open-mindedness aspect, likewise only the analyticity aspect for school variable and open-mindedness and truth-seeking for trainings attended variable. All the rest, the findings showed that school, gender, year level, position held, course and trainings attended are not considered factors that could affect the student leaders' perception on leadership.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The perception of student leaders on leadership presented in the study are commendable; thus, these must be reviewed further and afterwhich these must be dessiminated in various platforms like webinar, virtual workshops and in-person conferences. The level of critical thinking disposition of student leaders could be measured not only through perception but also through activities performed as a result of these manifestations of desirable leadership traits. For future studies then, it is recommended that measurement must not be done only through perception but some situational analysis of various conditions as well. For future studies, it is recommended to increase the number of respondents and make sure that the profile variables would have a balance frequency or percentage. Most of the recommendations on leadership enhancement are integrated in the proposed LEAD program in the utilization part of WEALTH 2.0 program. Thus, this is highly recommended for review and eventual utilization or adaption.

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